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“TECHNOLOGY MEETS TEACHING: THE RISE OF AI IN EDUCATION”

Artificial Intelligence is rapidly transforming many aspects, especially on our generation today - including education. With the development of advanced technologies, AI is becoming a powerful tool that helps improve the way for students to learn and teachers teach. Because of its ability to personalize learning, increase accessibility, and support educators, artificial intelligence is likely to play a major role in the future of education.

However, Artificial Intelligence should not completely replace teachers. Teachers provide guidance, emotional support, and critical thinking development that technology cannot fully replicate. They also help students develop social skills, values, and creativity, which are essential parts of education.

Furthermore, Artificial Intelligence and Human has a really big difference. Yet, there are things that Human can do that technologies can. And there are things that technologies can do, but humans cannot.

In conclusion, Artificial Intelligence has the potential to improve education by making learning more personalized and accessible. But, it should support teachers rather than replacing them, ensuring a balanced and effective learning environment for every students - as they deserve it.